

Preparation of the Solvates of Metal Acetates with Acetic Anhydride

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Alkali metal acetates form solvates of composition $CH_3COOM.Ac_2O$ while transition metal acetates form solvates of composition $(CH_3COO)_2.M.2Ac_2O$ with acetic anhydride. In the case of alkali metals, the solvent molecule is held up by ion-dipole interaction while in the case of transition metal, the solvent molecules are held up by coordination. This is evidenced by λ_m and I. r. studies.

SOLUTION chemistry in acetic anhydride has been investigated extensively laying emphasis on the role played by the autoionisation of the solvent¹⁻⁷. Paul and his coworkers⁸ have reported the formation of adducts of Lewis acids and bases with acetic anhydride and from i.r. studies, their structures have been elucidated. Some double acetates of metals containing varying number of acetic anhydride molecules have been isolated and characterised^{9,10} but no attempt seems to have been made to isolate the solvates of metal acetates. In the present communication, we report the isolation and characterisation of the solvates of metal acetates with acetic anhydride.

Acetic anhydride and metal acetates were purified by the methods reported earlier¹⁰. Solvates were prepared by the method of Paul and his coworkers^{11, 12}. Solvates isolated in the present studies are given in Table I. Their composition has been established by elemental analysis.

Results and Discussion

Process of solvation results in the attachment of the solvent molecule or molecules to the cation, the anion or the molecule of the solute as a whole through coordination, ion-dipole interaction or possibly ion induced dipole interaction. If these interactions are strong enough, it results in the formation of solid solvates and the solvent is drawn into the lattice of the solid compound.

Most of the ionising and coordinating solvents are well known to form solvates with various compounds¹¹⁻¹⁴. Amphoteric behaviour of acetic anhydride enables it to form solvates with a variety of compounds. Except for the solvates of the acetates of alkali metals, most of the isolated solvates are either insoluble or have low solubility in acetic anhydride and the solutions formed are low conducting. Solvates of the transition metal acetates are insoluble in nitrobenzene and nitro-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE SOLVATES OF METAL ACETATES

Compound	Solvate	m pt. (°C)	Colour	% Found			% Required			Molar Conductance in DMF, ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	First dissolution temperature in T.G.A. (°C)
				C	H	Metal	C	H	Metal		
Ni(OAc) ₂	Ni(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	98 D	Blue	31.68	4.25	31.88	32.38	4.05	13.20	—	188
Pb(OAc) ₂	Pb(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	58 D	White	24.24	3.14	34.24	24.60	3.03	34.92	—	172
Cd(OAc) ₂	Cd(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	112 D	White	28.52	3.44	22.32	28.86	3.51	22.55	—	178
Hg(OAc) ₂	Hg(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	72 D	Brown	24.20	3.18	34.66	24.54	3.24	34.18	—	166
Zn(OAc) ₂	Zn(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	84 D	White	31.24	3.82	14.76	31.83	3.98	14.52	—	176
Co(OAc) ₂	Co(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	75 D	Rosy Pink	32.16	3.96	13.64	32.38	4.04	13.24	—	192
Mg(OAc) ₂	Mg(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	122 D	White	34.98	4.16	5.44	35.26	4.38	5.92	—	152
Ca(OAc) ₂	Ca(OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	—	White	33.58	4.21	9.86	33.78	4.41	9.45	—	178
CH ₃ COOLi	CH ₃ COOLi.Ac ₂ O	105-7	White	35.84	4.36	3.18	36.08	4.49	3.45	165	162
CH ₃ COONa	CH ₃ COONa.Ac ₂ O	6	White	33.16	4.02	10.76	33.33	4.16	10.65	188	152
CH ₃ COOK	CH ₃ COOK.Ac ₂ O	144	White	40.92	3.64	16.74	41.08	3.87	16.82	222	158
CH ₃ COONH ₄	CH ₃ COONH ₄ .Ac ₂ O	66	White	33.82	6.04	—	34.12	6.16	—	208	150
CH ₃ COORb	CH ₃ COORb.Ac ₂ O	88	White	25.42	3.14	30.68	25.85	3.23	30.70	215	152
CH ₃ COOTl	CH ₃ COOTl.Ac ₂ O	123	White	17.86	2.18	50.88	18.11	2.26	51.43	198	146
CH ₃ COOCs	CH ₃ COOCs.Ac ₂ O	96	White	21.72	2.38	39.38	22.08	2.76	40.03	218	148

methane; their molar conductance values could not be determined. Solvates of alkali metal acetates on the other hand are soluble in acetic anhydride and λ_m values are quite high considering the moderate dielectric constant of the solvent.

Acid anhydride shows two carbonyl absorption bands, the position, separation and the intensities of which depend upon whether it is conjugated or cyclic anhydride¹⁵. In acetic anhydride, these bands are observed at 1824 and 1748 cm^{-1} .

metals. I.r. spectra of the solvates of alkali metal acetates show all these bands in the same spectral region as present in sodium acetate¹⁹. Difference in the asymmetric and symmetric carboxylate stretching modes is of the same order as observed in sodium acetate which rules out any acetate coordination with alkali metals. But in the case of the solvates of transition metals acetates, the bands that could be assigned to the free acetate group¹⁷ are missing. The extent of the separation of the asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes

TABLE 2 (A)—PRINCIPAL BANDS OF THE CARBOXYLATE IONS FOR VARIOUS SOLVATES

	LiOAc.Ac ₂ O	NaOAc.Ac ₂ O	KOAc.Ac ₂ O	RbOAc.Ac ₂ O	CsOAc.Ac ₂ O	NH ₄ OAc.Ac ₂ O	TlOAc.Ac ₂ O
CO ₂ (cm ⁻¹) (Asymmetric)	1588	1603	1625	1635	1624	1628	1622
CO ₂ (cm ⁻¹) (Symmetric)	1426	1418	1405	1400	1398	1400	1398

TABLE 2 (B)

	Zn (OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	Cd (OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	Hg (OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	Mg (OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	Ca (OAc) ₂ .2Ac ₂ O	Ni (OAc) ₂ . 2Ac ₂ O	Co (OAc) ₂ . 2Ac ₂ O
CO ₂ (cm ⁻¹) (Asymmetric)	1615	1618	1620	1615	1618	1622	1614
CO ₂ (cm ⁻¹) (symmetric)	1413	1416	1416	1400	1403	1406	1402

In addition, strong band due to C-O-C stretching mode is observed in the region 1175-1045 cm^{-1} . In the case of the solvates of alkali metals, bands due to ethereal O-C stretching mode and one of the carbonyl stretching modes at 1748 cm^{-1} are not affected. The other carbonyl stretching mode present at 1824 cm^{-1} shifts to lower region 1812 to 1802 cm^{-1} . The shift in the carbonyl stretch is maximum in the case of lithium acetate solvate and minimum in the case of thallos acetate solvate. This lowering of carbonyl stretching mode is due to strong ion-dipole interaction between the positively charged cation and acetic anhydride which is maximum in the case of highly polarised cation lithium. This observation is supported by T.G.A. studies of these solvates. Dissociation temperature of these solvates is a measure of the strength of the ion-dipole interaction between the two components. It is observed that the dissociation temperature of LiOAc.Ac₂O is 162° while that of TlOAc.Ac₂O is 146°. In the case of the solvates of the transition metal acetates, only one of the carbonyl stretching mode of acetic anhydride is lowered from 1824 to 1760-1780 cm^{-1} while the other mode at 1748 cm^{-1} is not affected. The ethereal oxygen ν (C-O-C) stretching mode is also shifted to higher spectral region suggesting that the solvent molecules are coordinated to the central metal atom through one of the carbonyl groups.

By comparing the i.r. spectrum of the acetate ion in compounds of known structures, it has been possible to distinguish between various acetate coordination¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In the present studies, attention has been focussed on the asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of the carboxylate groups in the solvates of the acetates of transition

of the carboxylate group is less than that for the free acetate group suggesting that acetate group is acting as symmetrical bidentate chelating group¹⁸. There is also evidence to show that the acetate group is acting as bridging bidentate ligand²¹ as well which finds support from their insolubility in various aprotic solvents. Most of these metals are known to have a coordination number of six. In these solvates, the central metal acquires a coordination number of six by coordinating with two molecules of acetic anhydride, the two acetate groups acting as chelating bidentate ligands or bridging group. Important bands for these metal acetate solvates are included in Table 2.

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References

1. R. C. PAUL, K. C. MALHOTRA and O. C. VAIDYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 1.
2. R. C. PAUL, K. C. MALHOTRA and O. C. VAIDYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 63.
3. R. C. PAUL, K. C. MALHOTRA and O. C. VAIDYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 97.
4. K. C. MALHOTRA and D. S. KATOCH, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 1413.
5. K. C. MALHOTRA and D. S. KATOCH, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1975, 28, 991.
6. G. JANDER, H. SCHMIDT and I. WITTKOPF, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1948, 256, 113.

7. M. USANOVICH and K. YATSMIRSKII, *J. Gen. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1941, 11, 95 4.
8. R. C. PAUL, R. C. SAWHNEY and S. L. CHADHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 556.
9. K. C. MALHOTRA and D. S. KATOCH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 550.
10. K. C. MALHOTRA and D. S. KATOCH, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1976 (In press).
11. R. C. PAUL, D. SINGH and S. S. SANDHU, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 315.
12. R. C. PAUL, M. S. BAINS and G. SING, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 183.
13. G. JANDER, E. RUSBERG and H. SCHMIDT, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1948, 255, 238.
14. R. C. PAUL and K. C. MALHOTRA, *Z. anorg. Chem.* 1963, 321, 56.
15. H. M. RANDALL, R. G. FLOWERS, N. FUSON and J. R. DANGL, "Infrared Determinations of Organic Structures", Van Nostrand, 1949. p. 368.
16. N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1579.
17. K. NAKAMOTO, P. J. MCCARTHY, A. RUBY and A.E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1066.
18. K. NAKAMOTO, F. FUJITA, S. TANAKA and M. KOBAYASHI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4904.
19. K. C. PATIL, G. V. CHANDRASEKHAR, M. V. GEORGE and G. N. R. RAO, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1968, 46, 257.
20. D. A. EDWARD and R. N. HAYWARD, *Canad J. Chem.*, 1968, 46, 3443.
21. D. LAWTON and R. MASON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 921.